

compost, and a urea-compost mixture. Rice varieties Ratna, Subarna, and IET1444 were used. A uniform 50 kg K/ ha was applied basally during land preparation. N as urea was applied in three equal splits; the entire amount of compost was added basally. A separate field experiment was conducted for each variety with three replications in a randomized block design.

Compost was effective in increasing yield (Table 2). Ratna gave the best response. Yields with urea were highest in all treatments; yields with compost alone and in combination with urea

Table 2. Response of rice to compost and urea. Calcutta. India.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
	Ratna	Subarna	IET1444
Control (no N)	3.1	3.5	3.7
Compost at 120 kg N/ha	5.2	4.7	5.4
Urea at 120 kg N/ha	5.3	5.1	5.6
Compost at 60 kg N/ha + urea at 60 kg N/ha	5.2	4.9	5.4
CD at 5%	0.2	0.2	0.2

^a Means of 2 yr.

were similar. The effect of compost on yield may be due to its appreciable amounts of N, P, K, Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu, along with organic matter. In

addition, increased available macro- and micronutrients in the soil ultimately help increase yield. □

Influence of herbicides on biomass production and relative growth rate of *Azolla pinnata*

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Field and pot culture experiments were used to study the effect of some promising preemergence herbicides on biomass production and relative growth rate (RGR) of azolla. Azolla was inoculated at 200 g/m² and fresh biomass was estimated 15 d later in the field. RGR was calculated from fresh weight in pot cultures at 3-d intervals.

Among the herbicides tried, biomass production was highest with EPTC alone (see table). Butachlor recorded

Effect of some herbicides on azolla biomass production. Coimbatore, India.

Herbicide	Biomass (t/ha) in field	RGR (g/g per d) in pot culture
EPTC	6.69	0.1818
EPTC + 2,4-D ethyl ester (EE)	6.51	0.1994
EPTC + 2,4-D butyl ester (BE)	6.47	0.1810
Molinate + 2,4-D (EE)	5.20	—
Molinate	4.86	—
Thiobencarb	4.05	—
Butachlor	2.96	—
No herbicide (control)	—	0.1974

the least biomass production. Thiobencarb, molinate, and combinations with 2,4-D EE were similar. Biomass production was significantly less than for EPTC and its combinations with 2,4-D esters.

Azolla inoculation 3 d after herbicide application recorded the

highest biomass; that on the day of herbicide application drastically reduced biomass production.

Applying EPTC either alone or in combination with 2,4-D esters and inoculating azolla 3-6 d after application produced the highest azolla biomass and higher RGR. □

Preparation method for carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium used to culture rice plant in water

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The pH value of media used in water culture of rice plants declines rapidly

because of nutrient absorption by rice roots. The pH must be adjusted almost every day, a time-consuming process. A more practical, carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium, containing large quantities of CO₂ has been developed. Similar conditions exist in field soil solutions.

In the new medium ammonium bicarbonate and potassium bicarbonate are used to lower the proportion of sulfate and chloride salts.

Stock solution A: Dissolve 113 g of ammonium bicarbonate (NH₄HCO₃)

and 31.9 g of potassium bicarbonate (KHCO₃) in 1 liter of distilled or CO₂-saturated water. Stir carefully and slowly to dissolve the chemicals and to prevent formation of heavy foam. Preserve this stock solution in polyethylene or glass bottles.

Stock solution B: Dissolve 40.0 g of Na₂HPO₄ in 1 liter of distilled water.

Stock solution C: Dissolve 36.7 g of MgSO₄·7H₂O in 1 liter of distilled water.

Stock solution D: Dissolve 15.1 g of Fe-EDTA and 10.5 g of CaCl₂·2H₂O in 1 liter of distilled water.

Mix 11 ml of stock solution A and 5.5 ml of stock solutions B, C, and D, and dilute with water to total 5.5 liters of medium. The final concentrations are shown in Table 1. Because the pH value of this solution is higher than 7.0, adjust pH by blowing CO₂ gas directly from a CO₂ cylinder into the bicarbonate solution. The pH declines to 5.2 within 3-4 min. The pH value adjusted by CO₂ bubbling depends on the salt composition of the diluting water, but generally varies from pH 5.2 to 5.5.

The pH of this carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium rises no more

Table 1. Composition of salts and concentration of elements in bicarbonate solution.

Element	Concentration		Salt
	ppm	mM	
N	40	2.85	NH ₄ HCO ₃
P	8.72	0.28	Na ₂ HPO ₄
K	24.9	0.64	KHCO ₃
Ca	2.86	0.071	CaCl ₂ •2H ₂ O
Mg	3.61	0.149	MgSO ₄ •7H ₂ O
Fe	2	0.036	Fe-EDTA

than 0.2-0.3 unit/d, even at the vegetative growth stage of rice plants, and adjustment by CO₂ gas bubbling is necessary only every 3-4 d during

Table 2. Dry mass of rice shoots cultivated in carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium for 2 mo.

Treatment	pH	Dry mass (g)
Kasugai medium ^a	6.6	133 ± 14
Carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium	6.6	140 ± 8
Carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium	5.5	132 ± 7

^aSources of N and K in Kasugai medium are ammonium sulfate and potassium chloride.

cultivation. Plant growth in this new medium was identical to that in the standard Kasugai medium (Table 2). □

Azolla growth relative to soil moisture

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Growth of azolla *A. pinnata*, Bangkok strain, was measured at different soil moisture levels. Five experimental treatments — 3-cm-deep water (control), saturated garden soil (with water film on the surface), moist garden soil, moist compost, and moist paddy soil — were used in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Polyethylene plastic sheets were laid beneath the soil in 1-m² plots to maintain the water level required in the 3-cm-deep and saturated treatments. Other plots were sprinkled as necessary. The experiment was kept in partial shade. Harvest was 20 d after stocking the azolla plants. The azolla crop was harvested by hand with most of the roots intact, washed to remove soil and other foreign matter, and

drained before the weight was recorded.

Fresh and sun-dried weights of 100 azolla plants from different growing media did not differ from each other (see table). Of the total biomass production, however, azolla grown on saturated garden soil, moist compost, and 3-cm-deep water had the highest fresh weight; plants grown on saturated garden soil recorded the

highest sun-dried weight. Azolla grown on saturated garden soil covered 98% of the experimental plot; that grown with 3-cm-deep water covered 95%. Dry weight percentage of harvested material did not vary among the treatments.

These results strongly suggest that azolla can be grown on saturated or moist media as productively as on water. □

Means^a of some growth components of azolla plants grown on different media, PSPC, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines.

Growing medium	100-plant weight (g)		Computed plant weight (t/ha)		Dry weight (%)	Matting ^b (%)
	Fresh	Sun-dried	Fresh	Sun-dried		
3-cm-deep water (control)	11	0.6	8.9 ab	0.62 b	6.8	95
Saturated garden soil	9	0.8	11.6 a	0.96 a	8.3	98
Moist garden soil	12	0.8	4.9 c	0.33 c	6.1	50
Moist compost	12	0.8	8.3 abc	0.62 b	7.5	80
Moist paddy soil	13	0.8	5.4 bc	0.26 c	4.8	75
Test of significance	ns	ns	1%	1%	ns	—
CV (%)	18	21.2	30.1	30.26	10.1	—

^aAv of 4 replications. Means having a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level. ^bVisual observation.

Management of Zn deficiency in lowland rice

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We sought a practical and efficient method of curing Zn deficiency in the field.

IR6 was transplanted on high pH (8.2) clay loam soil with low organic matter (0.55%) and a cation exchange

capacity of 28 meq/ 100 g soil. Available DTPA-extractable Zn in the soil was 0.75 ppm. Fertilizer was 120-26-0 kg NPK/ ha. The lowest Zn deficiency symptoms and the highest yields were recorded in the treatments